

DIVIDEND POLICY AND FIRM VALUE: EVIDENCE FROM SELECT PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANIES IN INDIA

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Abstract

Dividend is a return to the equity shareholders from the portion of profits of the company for their investment in shares. The main objective of the study is to analyze “The impact of dividend policy on firm value of select Pharmaceutical Companies in India”. A Sample of top ten Pharmaceutical Companies is selected on the basis of criteria: Highest debt (Rs: in Crores), BSE Listed Companies and Dividend declared for continuous 10 years. A study period of 10 years from 2012-2013 to 2021-2022 was taken. The “Dividend Yield Ratio” and “Dividend Payout Ratio” are taken as independent variables to measure the Dividend Policy and Tobin’s Q, Price to book Ratio and Price Earnings Ratio is taken as dependent variables to assess the Firm Value. The Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Panel Data Regression Analysis are applied to analyze the data. The findings were presented in this Research Paper. The Pharmaceutical Industry faces challenges like Lack of stable pricing, Policy environment and lack of capabilities in the innovation space. The appropriate dividend policy will help the new shareholders to invest and helps to overcome the challenges faced by Pharmaceutical Companies. It will help the pharmaceutical companies to enhance the firm value. This will lead to growth of pharmaceutical industry and economic development of India.

Keywords: Dividend Policy, Firm Value and Pharmaceutical Companies in India.

Introduction

The dividend is the most important part of a company's long-term financial approach. It is a payment made to shareholders in exchange for their willingness to take risks inversely related to the level of risk taken ‘(Lipson et al, 1998)’. One of the most difficult decisions has been decision on dividend. One important facet of corporate finance. Dividend policy is one of several elements that influence a company's worth. A dividend or Return on capital is paid to shareholders. The basic purpose of dividend policy is to maximise the wealth of shareholders. Dividend distribution and policy are always key considerations. Every corporate organisation, investor, researcher, and funding agency, among others, should be concerned about this issue. Over the course of the year, different ideas on financial economics have been proposed by financial economists (Miller & Modigliani, 1961).

Theoretical Background

1. Dividend Irrelevance Theory

According to Miller and Modigliani's Irrelevance Theory(1961), The "Dividend has no association on the firm's value" ,which is determined by current and future cash flows.

2. Bird in the hand Theory

Gordon suggested this hypothesis (1959).It argues that "Dividend has a huge effect on the firm's valuation" and that is the cost of doing business.

3. Pecking Order Theory

The "Issuance of equity", on the other hand, sends a negative signal that the stock is overvalued and that management is looking to raise funds by diluting company shares.

4. Agency Cost Theory

Easterbook (1984) assumes that there is no transaction cost brokerage cost and Agency cost. This says dividend has a direct association between Dividend Payout and Business Concern.

Statement of the Problem

Dividends are viewed by investors as a sign of future growth and well-managed companies. The regular payout has a favourable impact on share prices, according to the relevance theory of dividends. As a result, firms that pay regular and significant dividends remain at the top of the investment list. A proper dividend policy would satisfy investors while also increasing the firm's worth. India's pharmaceutical industry is expected to reach a market size of US\$ 100 billion by 2025, because of increased consumer spending, growing urbanisation, and rising healthcare insurance. India's pharmaceutical business contributed 1.30 percent of GDP between 1991 and 2013.The Pharmaceutical Industry faces challenges like Lack of stable pricing, Policy environment and lack of capabilities in the innovation space. The appropriate dividend policy will help the new shareholders to invest and helps to overcome the challenges faced by Pharmaceutical Companies. The major perspective of the research is to know how the "Dividend Policy" affects the Firm Value. The present study "Dividend Policy and Firm Value: Evidence from select Pharmaceutical Companies in India" is carried out to fill the research gap.

Literature Review

Mr.Kathari Santosh(2021) reveals that "Dividend Policy" has a considerable impact on dividend payout and business profitability, as well as increasing shareholder wealth.Venkata Mrudula Bhimavarapu, Shailesh Rastogi(2021) noticed that Dividend Payout Ratio is significantly associated with the Non Performing Asset in the banks. Kanakriyah(2020) demonstrated that the "Dividend Policy has a optimistic influence on the financial performance of the firm". Harish Kumar Singla (2019) discovered that "Growth", "lifespan"

has a optimistic influence on “Dividend Policy”. Dividend Payout is influenced by the “firm's growth” and “Profitability”.Kolawole, E. (2018) discovered that “Dividend Payout” and “Retention Ratios” have a optimistic impact on “Earning Per Share”. “Dividend policy” have a considerable impact on the company valuaion, according to Dr. D Geetha and A Karthika(2017). Labhane and Mahakud (2016) revealed that dividend payout ratio has a productive influence, when investment options are limited in a study of 781 publicly traded Indian companies.P.G.Thirumagal and S. Vasantha (2016) discovered that a dividend, liquidity,company's risk and affect shareholder's value. The earnings of the companies and size were tiny in comparison to the riches of the shareholders. According to Navita Nathani and Ritu Gangil (2019), the dividend payout ratio is influenced by retained earnings, investment opportunities, liquidity/cash flow and dividend distribution tax.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the association between Dividend Policy and Firm Value
2. To analyze the impact of Dividend Policy on Firm Value

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no impact of Dividend Policy on Firm Value

H₁: There is an impact of Dividend Policy on Firm Value

Breush – Pagan LM Test

H₀₂: If P>0.05, there is no significant so Pooled OLS Regression is accepted

H₂: If P<0.05, there is a significant so Random Effect Model is accepted

Hausman Test:

H₀₃: If P>0.05, there is no significant so Random Effect Model is accepted

H₃: If P<0.05, there is a significant so Fixed Effect Model is accepted

Model Framed

“Y = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$ ”

“Y = Dependent Variable, β_0 =Constant, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Coefficient of explanatory variable, X= Independent Variable and e= Error Term”

TQ= $\beta_0 + \beta_1 DPR + \beta_2 DYR + \beta_3 PER + \beta_4 FS + \beta_4 GROWTH + \beta_4 PR + e$

Materials and Methods

Sample: A sample of top ten Pharmaceutical Companies in India was selected on the basis of criteria:

- i) Highest Debt (March 2021)
- ii) BSE Listed Companies
- iii) Dividend declared continuously for ten years

Companies	Highest Debt
1. Sun Pharma	Rs: 5615.12
2. Torrent Pharma	Rs: 3145.14
3. Glenmark	Rs: 3304.67
4. Cadila	Rs: 898.10
5. Lupin	Rs: 707.16
6. Ind Swift	Rs: 660.58
7. Work hardt	Rs: 686.35
8. Laurus Labs	Rs: 561.32
9. Jubilant	Rs: 442.00
10. Alembic Pharma	Rs: 398.47

A2

The table-2 reveals that the “Mean”, “Standard Deviation”, “Variance”, “Kurtosis”, and “Skewness” of BSE Listed Companies for the study period of 2012 to 2021. The mean of DPR (59.06) which indicates that they issue dividend more than half percentage. The Std deviation of DYR (562.294), PER (0.205) is less than the mean value which indicates that they are not closely related. The Variance of DPR (8.33) and Price to Book Ratio (11.21) is less than the mean value. So, there is a consistency in issuing Dividend and its financial efficiency. The DYR and Tobin’s Q is negatively skewed and DPR, PER and PBR are positively skewed. In Kurtosis, Size are called Platykurtic because, they have negative values. In kurtosis DPR, DYR, PER, PBR and Tobin’s are greater than 1. So they are called leptokurtic.

A3

The table 3 portrait the correlation matrix of select Pharmaceutical Companies. At 1% Significance level, “Dividend Payout Ratio” is related with “Tobin’s Q” and “Profitability” is significant with “Tobin’s Q” at 5% level. “Price Earning Ratio”, “Size” and “Growth” have no association with Tobin’s Q. A high dividend payout ratio does not always imply that the company is doing well. High dividend payouts may be interpreted by investors as an indication of the company's failure to adequately manage its free cash flow. Investor perceptions like this might lower a company's value.

A4

From the table 4, the Breush-Pagan test shows that Cross section and Time Series are not significant. “Hence, alternative hypothesis H1 is rejected and Null hypothesis, If $P > 0.05$, there is no significant so Pooled OLS Regression is accepted”.

A5

From table-5, it has been found that the DYR is negatively correlated with TQ. Hence Null Hypothesis H01 is rejected and alternative hypothesis, “There is a significant effect of Dividend Policy on Firm Value is accepted” R-Square value (0.1693) has 16% variation in TQ. F-Statistic (3.160) with Probability value (0.007) shows that the model is fit.

$$\text{TQ} = 6.510 - 0.528\text{DPR}$$

A6

From the A6-table 6, the Breush-Pagan test shows that Cross section and Time Series are not significant. “Hence, alternative hypothesis H1 is rejected and Null hypothesis, If $P > 0.05$, there is no significant so Pooled OLS Regression is accepted”.

A7

From A7-table 7, it has been found that the DPR is negatively correlated with PER. “Hence Null Hypothesis H01 is rejected and alternative hypothesis, there is a significant effect of Dividend Policy on Firm Value is accepted”. The R-Square value has 3.7% variation in PER. F-Statistic (2.456) with Probability value (0.001) shows that the model is fit.

$$\text{PER} = 12.536 + 112.72\text{DYR} + 10.463\text{GR}$$

Results and Discussion

1. At 1% significant level, Dividend Payout Ratio has an association with Tobin’s Q.
2. “Dividend Payout Ratio” has a negative impact and “Growth” has a effective influence on “Tobin’s Q”.
3. At 5% level of significance, Profitability is associated negatively with Tobin’s Q.

4. Variance of “Dividend Per Share” is less than mean, So there is consistency in dividend earnings.
5. In kurtosis, “Dividend Payout Ratio”, “Dividend Yield Ratio”, “Price Earnings Ratio”, “Growth”, “Profitability” and “Tobin’s Q” are greater than 1. So they are called leptokurtic
6. The positive and significant association between growth opportunities (GWOP) and company value suggests that firms with more GWOP have higher firm value.
7. The select Pharmaceutical Companies should increase their profitability and dividend payouts to increase their market value.
8. In order to make better payments for shareholders they should increase their productivity.
9. The firm with higher capacity to pay interest maintains higher liquidity.

Conclusion

The present research study examines the effect of “Dividend Policy” on the stock valuation of a few Indian pharmaceutical companies. The “Growth” and “Dividend Yield Ratio” have an influence on the company valuation and the research is important for lenders, managers, investors and stakeholders, because dividends aren't just a source of income for them; they're also a way to assess companies from an investing perspective. The findings are crucial for management in developing a dividend policy that maximises shareholder wealth. The Development of Pharmaceutical companies helps to the enhance the economy.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationship that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. There was no external fund received for the study. There is no conflict of interest.

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A1

Table: 1 Variable Description

Variables	Measures
Dividend payout ratio	Dividend per share to earnings per share
Dividend yield ratio	Dividend per share to market value per share
Price to book ratio	Market price per share/book value per share
Price earnings ratio	Share price to earnings per share
Tobin's q	Market value of equity + book value of preferred stock + book value of debt/book value of total asset

Source: i.m.pandey book

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Table: 2 – Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std dev	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
PER	748.96	168.43	2.837	3.074	8.366
PBR	7.618	13.278	176.31	3.230	10.643
TOBIN'S Q	5.951	6.313	39.855	1.648	2.611
DPR	21.365	13.059	170.55	2.353	12.537
DYR	0.512	1.776	3.157	5.809	36.057

Source: Computed Data

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Table: 3 Correlation Matrix

	PER	PBR	TOBIN'S Q	DPR	DYR
PER	1	-.127	0.469**	0.248*	-0.090
PBR	-0.127	1	0.045	-0.218*	0.718**
TOBIN'S Q	0.469**	0.045	1	0.012	0.071
DPR	0.248*	-0.218*	0.012	1	-0.154
DYR	-0.090	0.718**	0.071	-0.154	1

Source: Computed Data

**at 1% level and * at 5% level

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Table: 4 Breush –Pagan Test

	Cross - Section	Time	Both
Breush – Pagan Statistics P- Value	235.1581 (0.0000)	4.253 (0.0392)	239.4119 (0.0000)
Hausman Test Chi-sq	0.471528		
Prob	0.7900		

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Table: 5 Random Effect Model of Tobin's Q

Dependent Variable : TQ		
Sample: 2012 to 2021		
Total Panel Observations:100 (Cross Section 10 x Periods 10)		
	Co-efficient	Probability
C	6.510	0.002
DPR	-0.029	0.326
DYR	-0.528	0.004
R- Squared	0.1693	
Adjusted R-Square	-0.008	
F-Statistic	3.160	
Probability	0.007	

A6

TABLE: 6 BREUSH –PAGAN TEST

	Cross - Section	Time	Both
Breush – Pagan Statistics P- Value	318.768 (0.0000)	4.306 (0.0380)	323.075 (0.0000)
Hausman Test Chi-sq	3.093412		
Prob	0.2129		

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TABLE: 7 RANDOM EFFECT MODEL OF PER

Dependent Variable : PER		
Sample: 2012 to 2021		
Total Panel Observations:100 (Cross Section 10 x Periods 10)		
	Co-efficient	Probability
C	62.520	0.2561
DPR	-0.097	0.046
DYR	-0.426	0.9190
R- Squared	3.784	
Adjusted R-Square	-0.020	
F-Statistic	2.456	
Probability	0.001	